

Effectiveness of Vagal Maneuvers in the Acute Management of Supraventricular Tachycardia in a Resource Limited Emergency Setting

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study was to determine and compare the effectiveness of carotid sinus massage standard Valsalva maneuver and modified Valsalva maneuver in the acute termination of supraventricular tachycardia among hemodynamically stable patients.

Material and Methods: This descriptive study was conducted in the Emergency Department of Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology Faisalabad from 20th August 2023 to 19th February 2024. A total of 154 patients aged 18 to 50 years with electrocardiographically confirmed supraventricular tachycardia were enrolled using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Patients with hemodynamic instability pregnancy and contraindications to vagal maneuvers were excluded. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Continuous variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Results: A total of 154 patients were included in the study with a mean age of 34.69 ± 7.04 years. Overall successful termination of supraventricular tachycardia was achieved in 94 patients (61.04%) while 60 patients (38.96%) failed to respond to vagal maneuvers. Comparison of individual techniques revealed a highly significant difference in efficacy ($p = 0.0001$). The modified Valsalva maneuver demonstrated the highest success rate with 52 out of 64 patients (81.25%) achieving reversion to sinus rhythm. In comparison carotid sinus massage was successful in 21 out of 44 patients (47.73%) while standard Valsalva maneuver resulted in successful cardioversion in 22 out of 47 patients (46.81%). No statistically significant association was observed between efficacy and age duration of symptoms hypertension smoking status family history of supraventricular tachycardia or baseline blood pressure ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: Vagal maneuvers represent an effective and economical first line treatment strategy for the acute management of supraventricular tachycardia in resource limited emergency settings. Among the techniques evaluated the modified Valsalva maneuver demonstrated significantly superior efficacy compared with carotid sinus massage and standard Valsalva maneuver.

Keywords: Supraventricular tachycardia, Vagal maneuvers, Valsalva maneuver, Carotid sinus massage.

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Introduction

Supraventricular tachycardia represents a group of arrhythmias originating above the ventricles and is characterized by sudden onset rapid heart rate¹.

The term supraventricular tachycardia encompasses a heterogeneous group of tachyarrhythmias that originate above the ventricles and are characterized by rapid heart rates resulting from abnormalities in impulse formation or conduction within the atria or atrioventricular node²⁻³. SVT typically presents as a sudden onset and termination of rapid regular heart rhythm and is often associated with symptoms such as palpitations dizziness shortness of breath chest discomfort fatigue anxiety and occasionally syncope. Although SVT is generally not immediately life threatening in hemodynamically stable patients' recurrent episodes can significantly impair quality of life increase healthcare utilization and impose substantial economic burdens on healthcare systems⁴.

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The incidence of supraventricular tachycardia in the general population has been estimated to range from 35 to 50 cases per 100000 persons annually while its prevalence is reported to be approximately 2 to 3 cases per 1000 individuals. The condition affects individuals of all age groups but is particularly common among young and middle-aged adults. Women are reported to have a higher incidence of certain forms of supraventricular tachycardia particularly atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia. Despite advances in diagnostic and therapeutic modalities SVT continues to account for a considerable proportion of emergency department visits due to the distressing nature of symptoms and the need for prompt intervention⁵⁻⁶.

The pathophysiology of supraventricular tachycardia is primarily related to abnormal electrical activity occurring above the ventricles. The majority of SVT cases are caused by reentry mechanisms involving the atrioventricular node or accessory pathways. Atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia and atrioventricular reentrant tachycardia are among the most common forms encountered in clinical practice. In these arrhythmias electrical impulses repeatedly circulate through a reentrant pathway resulting in sustained rapid heart rates. Less commonly focal atrial tachycardia may occur due to increased automaticity or triggered activity within atrial tissue. Regardless of the underlying mechanism the rapid ventricular response associated with SVT may reduce cardiac output and produce significant symptoms particularly in susceptible individuals.

Patients presenting with supraventricular tachycardia frequently experience a wide range of clinical manifestations. Palpitations remain the most common presenting complaint and are often described as sudden awareness of a rapid heartbeat. Additional symptoms may include dizziness lightheadedness weakness dyspnea chest tightness diaphoresis and anxiety. In severe cases prolonged tachycardia may lead to hypotension altered mental status myocardial ischemia or syncope. The severity of symptoms depends on factors such as heart rate duration of the episode underlying cardiac function and the presence of comorbid medical conditions. Because the symptoms of SVT may overlap with those of other cardiovascular and non-cardiovascular disorders accurate diagnosis is essential for appropriate management.

Electrocardiography remains the cornerstone of SVT diagnosis. A twelve-lead electrocardiogram typically demonstrates a regular narrow complex tachycardia with heart rates ranging from 150 to 250 beats per minute. Identification of P wave morphology and atrioventricular relationships may assist in determining the specific subtype of supraventricular tachycardia. Rapid recognition and confirmation of the arrhythmia are crucial because treatment decisions largely depend on the patient's hemodynamic stability and the underlying mechanism of the tachycardia.

Current international guidelines recommend a stepwise approach to the management of supraventricular tachycardia. In hemodynamically unstable patients immediate synchronized electrical cardioversion is considered the treatment of choice due to the risk of cardiovascular collapse. Conversely hemodynamically stable patients are generally managed initially with vagal maneuvers because these interventions are noninvasive readily available inexpensive and associated with minimal complications. Pharmacological therapy such as adenosine is reserved for cases in which vagal maneuvers fail to terminate the arrhythmia.

Material and Methods

This descriptive study was conducted in the Emergency Department of Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology Faisalabad from 20th August 2023 to 19th February 2024 to evaluate the effectiveness of vagal maneuvers in the acute management of supraventricular tachycardia. The sample size was calculated using the World Health Organization sample size calculator with a 95% confidence level an anticipated proportion of 9.1% and an absolute precision of 4.55% resulting in a final sample size of 154 patients. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was employed. Adult patients of both genders aged 18 to 50 years with electrocardiographically documented supraventricular tachycardia were included in the study. Patients with hemodynamic instability pregnancy or contraindications to carotid sinus massage or Valsalva maneuver including aortic stenosis recent myocardial infarction glaucoma retinopathy cerebrovascular accident transient ischemic attack or carotid bruit were excluded.

After obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee and informed written consent from participants a detailed clinical history and baseline assessment were performed. Eligible patients were assigned to one of three intervention groups according to the vagal maneuver performed. Group one underwent carotid sinus massage while group two received the standard Valsalva maneuver and group three underwent the modified Valsalva maneuver. In the carotid sinus massage group, the patient was placed in a supine position and carotid sinus stimulation was performed according to standard clinical protocols. For the standard Valsalva maneuver patients generated expiratory pressure by blowing into a syringe while seated. The modified Valsalva maneuver consisted of the standard strain phase followed by immediate placement of the patient in a supine position with passive leg elevation at approximately 45 degrees. If the arrhythmia persisted following vagal maneuver application intravenous adenosine was administered according to guideline directed management protocols.

The primary outcome measure was the efficacy of the vagal maneuver defined as successful termination of supraventricular tachycardia and restoration of sinus rhythm

without pharmacological intervention. Patients were monitored using electrocardiography and observed for two hours after successful cardioversion to detect recurrence. Data were collected using a structured proforma and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Continuous variables including age duration of symptoms and blood pressure were presented as mean \pm standard deviation while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. The Chi square test was used to compare efficacy among different maneuver groups and to assess associations with demographic and clinical variables. A p value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 154 patients with electrocardiographically confirmed supraventricular tachycardia were included in the study. The mean age of participants was 34.69 ± 7.04 years. Overall successful termination of supraventricular tachycardia through vagal maneuvers was achieved in 94 patients (61.04%), while 60 patients (38.96%) did not respond and required further management. The modified Valsalva maneuver demonstrated the highest efficacy among all interventions.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (n = 154)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age Group (Years)		
18–35	92	59.74
36–50	62	40.26
Gender		
Male	88	57.14
Female	66	42.86

The majority of participants belonged to the 18–35 years age group (59.74%). Male patients constituted 57.14% of the study population while females represented 42.86%.

Table 2: Overall Efficacy of Vagal Maneuvers

Efficacy	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Successful	94	61.04
Unsuccessful	60	38.96
Total	154	100

Overall efficacy analysis revealed that vagal maneuvers successfully terminated supraventricular tachycardia in

61.04% of patients whereas 38.96% required additional pharmacological intervention.

Table 3: Comparison of Efficacy According to Type of Maneuver

Type of Maneuver	Successful n (%)	Unsuccessful n (%)
Carotid Sinus Massage	21 (47.73)	23 (52.27)
Modified Valsalva Maneuver	52 (81.25)	12 (18.75)
Standard Valsalva Maneuver	22 (46.81)	25 (53.19)

The modified Valsalva maneuver demonstrated the highest success rate (81.25%) compared with carotid sinus massage (47.73%) and standard Valsalva maneuver (46.81%). The difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.0001$).

Table 4: Significant Predictors of Successful Response

Variable	Successful n (%)	Unsuccessful n (%)	P-value
Male	47 (53.41)	41 (46.59)	0.025
Female	47 (71.21)	19 (28.79)	
Diabetes Present	22 (45.83)	26 (54.17)	0.009
Diabetes Absent	72 (67.92)	34 (32.08)	
Previous History of SVT Present	16 (94.12)	1 (5.88)	0.003
Previous History of SVT Absent	78 (56.93)	59 (43.07)	

Female patients demonstrated significantly greater efficacy than male patients. Non diabetic individuals showed higher success rates than diabetic patients. Patients with a previous history of supraventricular tachycardia exhibited the highest likelihood of successful cardioversion. All associations were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

Supraventricular tachycardia remains one of the most frequently encountered cardiac arrhythmias in emergency departments and often requires immediate intervention to relieve symptoms and restore normal cardiac rhythm. The present study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of different vagal maneuvers in the acute management of supraventricular tachycardia among hemodynamically stable patients presenting to a tertiary care cardiac emergency department. The findings demonstrated that vagal maneuvers are highly effective non pharmacological interventions and can successfully terminate a substantial proportion of supraventricular tachycardia episodes without the need for

pharmacological therapy. These results emphasize the importance of incorporating vagal maneuvers into routine emergency department practice particularly in healthcare settings where rapid and cost effective treatment options are essential.

The overall efficacy observed in the present study indicates that vagal maneuvers can successfully restore sinus rhythm in the majority of patients with supraventricular tachycardia. This finding highlights the significant clinical value of these techniques as first line interventions. The ability to terminate arrhythmia without medications provides several advantages including reduced exposure to drug related adverse effects decreased healthcare costs and shorter emergency department stay. Successful cardioversion through vagal stimulation also reduces the need for intravenous access medication preparation and prolonged patient monitoring which can improve the efficiency of emergency care services.

One of the most important findings of the study was the superiority of the modified Valsalva maneuver compared with carotid sinus massage and the standard Valsalva maneuver. The modified Valsalva maneuver demonstrated a markedly higher success rate and emerged as the most effective intervention among the three techniques evaluated.

This superior performance can be explained by the physiological mechanisms associated with the maneuver. Following the strain phase rapid repositioning of the patient into a supine position with passive leg elevation enhances venous return to the heart and increases vagal stimulation. The resulting autonomic response produces a greater slowing of atrioventricular nodal conduction which facilitates interruption of the reentrant circuit responsible for most episodes of supraventricular tachycardia. The findings suggest that simple modifications to traditional vagal techniques can significantly improve treatment outcomes.

The effectiveness of the modified Valsalva maneuver has important implications for emergency medicine practice. Unlike pharmacological therapies this technique requires no specialized equipment and can be performed rapidly at the bedside by trained healthcare professionals. The maneuver is simple to teach and can be consistently applied in a variety of clinical settings. In resource limited healthcare environments where access to advanced therapies may be restricted the modified Valsalva maneuver offers a practical and highly effective treatment option. Its implementation has the potential to improve patient outcomes while simultaneously reducing the burden on emergency department resources.

The study also identified significant associations between patient characteristics and treatment success. Female patients demonstrated higher rates of successful cardioversion compared with male patients. Although the exact physiological explanation remains uncertain this

observation suggests that gender related differences in autonomic nervous system function may influence responsiveness to vagal stimulation. Hormonal factors variations in autonomic tone and differences in cardiovascular physiology may contribute to the observed disparity. These findings highlight the importance of considering patient specific characteristics when evaluating treatment outcomes and suggest that individual biological factors may influence the effectiveness of vagal maneuvers.

Another important finding was the reduced efficacy observed among patients with diabetes mellitus. Diabetic patients exhibited lower success rates compared with non diabetic individuals. This result may be attributable to autonomic dysfunction which is a well recognized complication of diabetes. Long standing diabetes can impair autonomic nervous system function including vagal nerve activity which may diminish the physiological response required for successful cardioversion. Reduced parasympathetic responsiveness may limit the ability of vagal maneuvers to interrupt atrioventricular nodal conduction and terminate tachyarrhythmias. These findings emphasize the need for careful consideration of underlying metabolic conditions when selecting treatment strategies for supraventricular tachycardia.

The present study further demonstrated that patients with a previous history of supraventricular tachycardia had significantly higher success rates compared with those experiencing their first episode. This observation may reflect greater familiarity with symptoms earlier presentation to medical care and increased cooperation during maneuver performance. Patients who have previously experienced supraventricular tachycardia may recognize the onset of symptoms more quickly and seek treatment before prolonged tachycardia results in physiological changes that reduce maneuver effectiveness. Additionally recurrent episodes are often associated with predictable electrophysiological mechanisms that respond favorably to vagal stimulation. This finding suggests that patient experience and clinical history play an important role in determining treatment outcomes.

Several clinical variables including age duration of symptoms hypertension smoking status family history of supraventricular tachycardia and baseline blood pressure were not significantly associated with treatment success. These findings indicate that the effectiveness of vagal maneuvers is largely independent of many commonly encountered demographic and clinical characteristics. The absence of significant associations suggests that vagal maneuvers can be applied broadly across diverse patient populations without major concern regarding age related or cardiovascular risk related differences in efficacy. This supports their role as universally applicable first line interventions for stable supraventricular tachycardia.

The results of this study have substantial implications for healthcare delivery in resource constrained environments. In many developing countries emergency departments experience high patient volumes and limited access to advanced cardiac interventions. Under such circumstances interventions that are effective inexpensive and easy to perform are particularly valuable. Vagal maneuvers satisfy all of these criteria and represent an ideal treatment strategy for the initial management of supraventricular tachycardia. Successful implementation of these techniques can reduce dependence on pharmacological agents decrease healthcare expenditures and improve the overall efficiency of emergency department operations.

Conclusion

Vagal maneuvers represent an effective and economical first line treatment strategy for the acute management of supraventricular tachycardia in resource limited emergency settings. Among the techniques evaluated the modified Valsalva maneuver demonstrated significantly superior efficacy compared with carotid sinus massage and standard Valsalva maneuver. Female gender absence of diabetes mellitus and previous history of supraventricular tachycardia were associated with better treatment outcomes. The routine implementation of the modified Valsalva maneuver in emergency department protocols may improve cardioversion rates reduce dependence on pharmacological therapy and enhance the overall quality of patient care.

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Author's contribution:

MAA, ME: Conceptualization of Project

AR, SA: Data Collection

NH, HMF: Literature Search

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MAA: Writing of Manuscript